

TEACHING OF SAINT PAUL AND ITS IMPACTS ON CHRISTIANITY

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Abstract

After having been ascended of Prophet Jesus Christ, a Jew namely Paul appeared on the scenario of Christianity and claimed to be an apostle of Jesus. His claim was rejected by true companions of Prophet Jesus but one of them namely Barnabas had testified Paul so he was also seen as a disciple of Prophet Jesus Christ. Having entered into Jesus' followers, Paul begun to preach their thoughts affirming them as Jesus' teachings. Paul presented a new salvation theory through Jesus' crucifixion which was differed from traditional Judaism. Additionally, he abolished all commandments of Torah and declared keeping faith on Jesus' atonement sufficient for salvation. Furthermore, he announced that Jesus is begotten son of God instead of prophet or man. His views about Jesus, Torah and other Jewish rituals had been considered blasphemy against Jewish religion so the companion of Jesus strictly opposed him but Paul's influence on Christian society continuously spread. Gathering great number of people, he isolated his cult from Jewish-Christianity and founded a new version of Christianity which was totally against Jesus teachings. In this article, it has been analyzed that how to spread Pauline thoughts in Christian societies and what did they influenced upon this religion.

Keyword: Saint Paul, Founder of Christianity, Pauline thoughts.

Introduction of Saint Paul:

Saint Paul is considered as the true founder of modern Christianity and he has such position in Christianity that even Jesus Christ does not have. The Jewish name of Saint Paul was Saul and he was originally from Judaism but as he converted to Christianity, he changed his name to Paul. In the time of his Jewishness, Saint Paul used to persecute the followers of Jesus. After heavenly ascension of Jesus Christ, Saint Paul claimed that he had made me his disciple by revelation on the way to Damascus. After this claim, Saint Paul joined the ranks of the disciples of Christine. The disciples were in shock at the miracle of the faith of the Saint Paul and were

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reluctant to give Saint Paul a place among them. However, testifying to Paul, a great disciple namely Barnabas added him to their group. Shortly after, the apostles joined the ranks of Christ, Saint Paul began to spread new ideas in the name of Jesus, which led to a heated argument between other disciples of Jesus and Paul, who eventually became Paul and his disciples. It led to the permanent separation between them. After separating from this group, Saint Paul began to openly spread his polytheistic ideas in the name of inspiration and revelation and wrote numerous letters to many churches established by Saint Paul, to promote these ideas.¹ Two hundred years later, Paul's letters became an integral part of the New Testament by declaring the church to be inspired, and today fourteen Pauline letters are part of the Christian New testament which was accepted by Christian world as inspired God's word. The ideological basis of the prevailing beliefs of Christianity is based on the texts of these letters rather than the teachings of Jesus. In this paper, we are going to discuss teachings of Saint Paul and its impact on Christianity.

Original Sin:

At the forefront of Pauline teaching is the original sin. The deed of eating fruit from the forbidden tree of Adam A.S (pbuh) and Eve (pbuh) to be the first sin of mankind. According to Pauline interpretation, God created man with good nature for his fellowship, but because of this sin God separated man from his fellowship and punished man with curse, hard work, suffering, pain, and death. Afflicted Being the noblest of human beings, all creatures also joined in this punishment. So, in the letter towards Romans, Saint Paul wrote:

"To be sure, sin was in the world before the law was given, but sin is not charged against anyone's account where there is no law. Nevertheless, death reigned from the time of Adam to the time of Moses, even over those who did not sin by breaking a command, as did Adam, who is a pattern of the one to come. But the gift is not like the trespass. For if the many died by the trespass of the one man, how much more did God's grace and the gift that came by the grace of the one man, Jesus Christ, overflow to the many."²

The result of this Pauline philosophy of sin is that all human beings are descendants of Adam. Since Adam (pbuh) committed a sin, that is why the children of Adam are inheriting this sin. All the children of Adam are equal partners in sin because they inherit sin. This sin leads man to death.³

Atonement:

Sin was inherited because of eternal sin. This sin continued to be transmitted to the children of Adam (peace be upon him). Now regarding the salvation of this sin, Saint Paul wrote that

"This is good, and pleases God our Savior, who wants all people to be saved and to come to a knowledge of the truth. For there is one God and one mediator between God and mankind, the man Christ Jesus, who gave himself as a ransom for all people. This has now been witnessed to at the proper time."⁴

According to the Saint Paul, the sacrifice of the life of Jesus Christ became the atonement for us, which freed us from inherited and eternal sin. Just as we were pushed into the punishment of eternal sin by the disobedience of an individual, so we became pure by the obedience of a single individual.⁵

In the first letter to the Corinthians, Saint Paul wrote:

“By this gospel you are saved, if you hold firmly to the word, I preached to you. Otherwise, you have believed in vain. For what I received I passed on to you as of first importance: that Christ died for our sins according to the Scriptures.”⁶

Impact the teaching of original sin and Atonement:

The sin that was committed by Adam in the Christian context. That sin had become an inherited sin and was passed down from generation to generation.

This belief had a profound effect on the Christian world. Christian scholars and pastors have been involved in many dangerous crimes. The latest example of this is the report published in BBC Urdu. According to the report, the clergy sexually abused 216,000 children, most of them boys, in France since 1950. This number is only for the clergy. If you count the other members of the church, this number could be around 330,000.⁷

According to this report, about two thousand nine hundred to three thousand two hundred clergymen have been found involved in this heinous act. This number is from France and there are many such incidents all over the world.

According to a BBC report, Pope Francis, the leader of the Catholic denomination, has announced an apology for the church's abusive behavior and sexual abuse.⁸

These are just a few of the many recent reports that have been written about the history of the church.

Sonhood:

In Christianity, Sonhood of Jesus Christ is major doctrine which was invented by Saint Paul. The Son is the word of God to the Christian. According to Christian beliefs, the knowledge of God is due to this attribute. This adjective is acting like a father. All things are created by this attribute, and this attribute is established and ancient. Saint Paul stated in his letter of Colossians that

“The Son is the image of the invisible God, the firstborn over all creation. For in him all things were created: things in heaven and on earth, visible and invisible, whether thrones or powers or rulers or authorities; all things have been created through him and for him. He is before all things, and in him all things hold together. And he is the head of the body, the church; he is the beginning and the firstborn from among the dead, so that in everything he might have the supremacy. For God was pleased to have all his fullness dwell in him.”⁹

The doctrine of sonhood and divinity was first stated in the Gospel of John with these words

“In the beginning was the Word, and the Word was with God, and the Word was God. He was with God in the beginning.”¹⁰

In Christianity, Jesus Christ is both God and man at a time. God created them with His Word and gave them human bodies so that they could be sacrificed to atone for the eternal sin of humanity. It is this doctrine of the Son that brings Jesus Christ to the place of God. God unravels the entanglement of the Son and the human incarnation in such a way that as a human being Jesus Christ had a lower status than God. That is why he said that

“For the Father is greater than I.”¹¹

That is why all human conditions were found in Jesus Christ. While as God they are equal to the Father. The Gospel of John also contains the statement of Jesus Christ:

“I and the Father are one.”¹²

Impact the teaching of Sonhood:

Christianity had a profound effect on this doctrine of Sonhood. The doctrine of Christ on behalf of the clergy was born. The clergy began to consider themselves independent because the clergy were God's vicegerent and had the right to govern. The clergy and the church came under the control of all walks of life. The church and the clergy, despite the state and the monarchy, were considered the be saint. The clergy had the confidence of the people. Even the rulers needed the church. The clergy had the power to subdue the government and government officials.¹³ According to a Christian scholar, the clergy even had the power to revoke any text they wanted and to make it the word of God.¹⁴

This same confidence later appeared to give rise to many flaws. The clergy began to misuse the claim of being God's vicegerent. Sincerity was replaced by desire. Apologies began to be distributed among the people as God's vicegerent. People would come and inquire about their sins. This apology was also considered a proof of entering Paradise. This is still going on today. People attend church and confess their sins to the pastor so that he can pray for them and prepare the means for their forgiveness and pave the way for heaven for them. The clergy began to take advantage of the situation by harassing the people and threatening to reveal their secrets.¹⁵

This power of distribution of apology became so wide that the clergy began to issue apology as a certificate, forgiving not only the living but also the dead. The situation became so bad that as soon as people put money in the vows, they would be given an apology with the sound of coins.¹⁶ In the same way, the treasury of the clergy increased and with the junior officials, the high officials of the clergy also started getting involved in this ugly act.¹⁷

In 1517 pastor named John Tetzl preached that if a Christian was involved in immorality with his mother, he should put a certain amount of money in the pastor's box of forgiveness. If

the pastor forgave this sin, then to God will also get rid of. ¹⁸ Thus, Christianity became a child's play.

While making money, the clergy suppressed every voice that spoke out against the Catholic Church. Such people and groups were suppressed by holding various councils and were dealt with severely by declaring them heretics and polytheists. Those who deviated from the Catholic faith were burned alive and their property confiscated. ¹⁹

For centuries, the church has kept itself above criticism and has become a dictatorial institution. The church did not change its ways, despite the many evils that pervaded the church, including corruption, immorality of clergy, and immorality, which led some to demand terminology in the church. The "Way Cliff Movement" was followed by the "John Huss" movement, which paved the way for the founding of the German Church, followed by Martin Luther. Initially, the church used force to stifle these opponents, but this stiffness intensified the religious reform movement, which resulted in the Protestant Church. The Protestant Church divided the pope's territorial power and the pope's power began to decline. The division of the pope's religious and political power also involved the interests of capitalists, rulers, politicians, and merchants, as the church excluded them from the economic sphere and sought to free themselves from church supremacy. Fully supported the Protestant Church. Later, when the Renaissance movement began, it shook the foundations of the church. During this period, both the pope and the church were excluded from politics and other social spheres, restricting them to the performance of churches and religious rites, and even today the clergy in the West are confined to the churches. The poor management of the church has not only deprived the pope of power but has also alienated society from religion. This same religious aversion later led the whole Western world to atheism, and today's Western society is based entirely on atheistic ideologies. It is the "doctrine of the Son of Jesus" and the "atonement of the Son of God". ²⁰

Allah, the Lord of the worlds, strongly condemned this ugly belief in the Qur'an

“And they say, The Most Merciful has taken [for Himself] a son. You have done an atrocious thing. The heavens almost rupture therefrom and the earth splits open and the mountains collapse in devastation.

That they attribute to the Most Merciful a son. And it is not appropriate for the Most Merciful that He should take a son.”²¹²²

Conclusion:

In this paper, teachings of Saint Paul have been discussed, in which he taught the doctrine of sonhood, in which Jesus Christ was made the Son of God and placed under the authority of God Almighty. This belief led to the sedition of papacy, where the clergy, using the authority of Christ, promoted fanaticism, which resulted in aversion to religion and the atheist movement. In addition to the doctrine of sonhood, the Holy Paul taught the doctrine of

atonement that Jesus Christ paid the penalty for our sins by dying on the cross. The sin that was committed by Adam in the Christian context. That sin had become an inherited sin and was passed down from generation to generation. This belief had a profound effect on the Christian world. Christian scholars and pastors have been involved in many dangerous crimes.

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